

A MICROMECHANICS BASED MODEL OF RESIN FLOW IN FABRIC WITH CROSS-FLOW AND OVER-FLOW EFFECTS

Rajendra Prasath, D Roy Mahapatra*

Department of Aerospace Engineering, Indian Institute of Science, Bangalore

* Corresponding author (droymahapatra@aero.iisc.ernet.in)

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1. Introduction

In this paper, a micromechanics model and a computational methodology are developed for resin transfer moulding (RTM) processes by accounting for the directional permeability tensor of the fabric. The model incorporates effective pore size of resin, over-flow, cross-flow, and race tracking in context of Darcy's law. Flow of resin through the fabric is modeled as flow through porous media [1, 2]. Here the Darcy's law and the additional effects (cross-flow, side-flow and race-tracking) is derived from the mass conservation law for an incompressible Newtonian fluid through the fabric. This approach aims to improve fabric based polymer composite process flow modelling. An important aspect in such context is the redistribution of resin during RTM process (associated change in porosity etc.) and ultimately the evolution of mechanical properties via cure kinetics. The mathematical model uses a minimal set of experimental data, which is obtained by performing a controlled experiment on a single configuration of fabric with flow under pressure gradient.

2. Modeling effective pore size

In published literature, porosity of the fabric has been assumed to be constant throughout the process of mould filling. However, it can be postulated that thermal transport through fiber bundles are dominant. Therefore, the surfaces of the fiber bundles or in other words the walls of the pores in the fabric experience initiation of polymerization of resin. As a result, the porosity of the fabric is expected to change. Hence, a recombination of the polymerizing resin by small-scale flow is likely. This effect is modeled by assuming the pore in the fabric as a cylinder of diameter D_0 and the change in

pore diameter is modeled as a function of time, pressure, viscosity and density of the resin. This approach is able to capture the instantaneous local porosity of the fabric.

3. Flow over fabric

Over-flow effect is modeled analytically considering unidirectional fibers in this paper. Apart from the resin infusion through the fabric, resin also flows above and below a fabric layer. Here only a single fabric layer is modeled for simplicity. This nature changes the flow front and velocity calculated only with the Darcy's equation based approach requires a consistent correction considering this over-flow effect. In the over-flow model, the flow is assumed to take place primarily through parallel conduit between two adjacent fibers. The diffusion equation derived above for flow through the fabric is rewritten to include the vacuum bag effect as a special effect of surface constraint. Similar effect due to mould surface can also be considered. The modified diffusion equation is then combined with the Hagen-Poiseuille equation to incorporate the effect of over flow in terms of mass conservation as well as the momentum conservation.

fig1: A schematic diagram describing the flow above and below the fabric.

4. Flow across fabric

Cross-flow or flow in the transverse direction with respect to the 0° fibers can occur due to gravity or pressure gradient. This can also alter the effective flow front in a similar way as discussed in context of over-flow.

fig 2: A schematic diagram describing the flow in the transverse direction with respect to the 0° fiber bundle.

This effect is modeled by considering flow over a periodic arrangement of alternate fiber and conduit flow as shown in the figure 2. The associated terms in the governing equations for diffusion and momentum conservation are rewritten.

5. Race tracking effect

Due to lower volume fraction of fibers along the mould wall, the resistance to the resin flow is relatively is decreased. As a result, the flow of resin is accelerated along the wall. This effect is called race-tracking effect. This effect is modeled as a flow through a rectangular duct of fixed dimensions (derived based on boundary thickness). The fully developed flow velocity in the rectangular duct and the velocity field in Darcy's equation for one dimensional porous media flow is combined to obtain the effective permeability of the assumed rectangular duct. A similar treatment has been reported in ref. [3]. Effect of over-flow and cross-flow is then implemented in the present formulation using the effective in-plane permeability due to race-tracking.

6. Finite element model

The governing equation for diffusion and momentum conservation are incorporated in a coupled field finite element model.

Experimentally estimated diffusion coefficient tensors are first used in a 2D finite element model of 2D single layer fabric. Effect of cross-flow as function of fiber angle and the micro-mechanical effect (cross-flow effect) are then validated by comparing the finite element simulation with experimental results for various different fiber angles. Results on the combined effect of over-flow, cross-flow and race-tracking toward edge and corners of the fabric layer are discussed. Experimental validation indicates good agreement with the modeling hypothesis and approach. For a more realistic predictive capability, the model needs to be extended to multiple fabric layers and through thickness effect. Various related issues and future direction of research are discussed.

References

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